

STORAGE RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE ECO-SYSTEM

2nd IREP Call Documentation - User

STORIES IREP1 POST RESEARCH QUESTIONNAIRE (WITH SATISFACTION SURVEY): USER (S)

After the StoRIES International Research Exchange Programme stay, users are required to submit a post research questionnaire. This should be done within 4 weeks after the Access is completed unless otherwise agreed. The Post Research Questionnaire form will be given to the User(s) by the Project Management. The report contains sections related to the work performed, the main results and observations that were achieved.

Summary questionnaire for users who have been granted International Research Exchange Programme (IREP) under the StoRIES project Horizon 2020 IREP scheme.

General information about the project	
Project title (as used in application)	Deep Learning for Automation of 3D Pore Analysis in Micro-CT Tomographs
Project acronym (max 15 characters)	UTILE-pore
StoRIES IREP RI(s) accessed	<i>University of Toronto, 5 King's College Road Toronto, Ontario M5S 3G8 Canada</i>
Keywords (up to ten, free text)	Artificial Intelligence, Deep Learning, Materials Engineering, Materials Characterization, Hydrogen Economy, Image Analysis
Arrival date (in town where RI located)	07.07.2024
Departure date (from town where RI located)	05.10.2024
Starting date of access (first day at RI)	08.07.2024
Finishing date of access (last day at RI)	04.10.2024

Number of days not using the RI (during the above period)	24
Reason for not using RI those days (describe)	Weekends
Number of days using the RI	65
Number of users granted access (group size)	1
Comments	
User	
User group leader or sole applicant (user group member 1)	
First name	
Last name	
Affiliation / Employer	IET-3, Forschungszentrum Jülich
Country of Employer	Germany
E-mail	
Comments	
User group member 2	
First name	
Last name	
Affiliation / Employer	
Country of Employer	
E-mail	
Comments	
User group member 3	
First name	
Last name	
Affiliation / Employer	
Country of Employer	
E-mail	
Comments	
User group member 4	
First name	
Last name	

Affiliation / Employer	
Country of Employer	
E-mail	
Comments	
Please insert more fields if your groups had more than four members.	
Access Summary Report - work performed and initial results	
Brief description of the objectives of your project (up to 200 words)	
<p><i>The primary objective of this project is to develop an automated AI-driven tool for the analysis of 3D gas diffusion layer (GDL) volumes from Proton Exchange Membrane Fuel Cells (PEMFCs). By leveraging high-resolution micro-CT imaging and convolutional neural networks (CNNs), the project aims to streamline the characterization of GDLs, which are crucial for effective water management and performance in fuel cells.</i></p> <p><i>The project will involve key steps, including the collection of micro-CT data, annotation of critical features such as pore spaces and materials, training machine learning models for segmentation and feature extraction, and developing visualization tools to interpret the results. Collaboration with Prof. Bazylak's research group will provide experimental expertise, while the AI-based methods will accelerate and enhance the accuracy of analysis. This approach will eliminate the traditional, time-consuming manual image analysis process and provide a more reliable and reproducible solution.</i></p> <p><i>The project also aims to deploy the resulting software on a cloud platform, making it accessible to the wider research community for use in PEMFC development, ultimately contributing to advancements in hydrogen energy technologies.</i></p>	
Activities performed (up to 600 words)	
<p>1 In-Person Characterization and Data Collection</p> <p><i>The first step involved acquiring high-resolution 3D volumes of GDLs using state-of-the-art micro-CT tomography equipment. This technique allows for the precise capture of the internal structure of the GDL, providing detailed insight into pore spaces, and material distribution. The instrumentation used was a micro-CT scanner, which allowed us to gather a complete view of the GDL's internal architecture. Data collection was performed with the collaboration of Prof. Bazylak's group, who provided experimental expertise to ensure the data's relevance and accuracy. This in-person characterization ensures that the 3D volumes represent the real structural properties of the GDL materials under study. For this study, we collected over 25 different CT scans from several commercially available GDLs with and without micro porous layer (MPL).</i></p> <p>2 Data Annotation and Parameter Identification</p> <p><i>After data acquisition, the next crucial step was to annotate the collected 3D micro-CT images. Annotation tools like LabKit and Napari were employed to meticulously classify different regions within the GDL volumes. Nevertheless, the final annotations were performed by calibrating the threshold of the CT scans with an external porosity measurement with a pycnometer to ensure the representation of the real structure in the training set. This process was vital for training the AI models since accurate annotations provide the basis for recognizing and segmenting these</i></p>	

features in unseen data. This phase also required an in-depth understanding of the GDL's microstructure and the performance-relevant features that need to be extracted, such as porosity, tortuosity, and permeability levels.

3 Model Finding, Training, Validation, and Testing

Once the annotated datasets were prepared, the next step was to select appropriate machine learning models. Several 3D convolutional neural networks (CNNs) were evaluated and benchmarked based on their performance on segmentation tasks. The models were trained using the annotated data to learn how to accurately identify and quantify the key parameters within the 3D volumes. Training the models involved using established AI frameworks such as **TensorFlow**, allowing for flexible experimentation with different architectures and configurations. During validation, the models were tested against a subset of the annotated data to ensure they could generalize well. Following validation, real-world testing of the trained models was conducted to evaluate their practical performance on new datasets.

4 Computer Vision-Based Feature Extraction

After the models were trained and validated, they were applied to the 3D GDL volumes for feature extraction. Computer vision techniques were employed to extract properties such as **porosity**, **tortuosity**, and **permeability** levels from the segmented volumes. Custom algorithms were developed to analyze the GDL structure and quantify these critical performance parameters. Furthermore, we enabled the analysis of the MPL in conjunction with the GDL in order to extract advanced metrics, such as MPL intrusion and MPL crack analysis. The extracted features provided meaningful insights into the water management and gas transport properties of the GDLs, crucial for optimizing PEMFC efficiency.

5 Development of Visualization Tools

Visualization tools were developed to make the data accessible and interpretable for researchers. Using 3D visualization like Visual Toolkit (VTK), interactive models were created that allowed users to explore the internal structure of the GDLs and analyze the extracted parameters. Additionally, graphs and plots summarizing key metrics, such as pore size distribution and tortuosity factors, were generated to facilitate data interpretation. The visualization tools enabled seamless communication of results between team members and allowed for deeper insight into the microstructure of the GDLs.

6 Pipeline Integration and Cloud Deployment

The final activity involved integrating all the developed components—data prediction, data analysis, feature extraction, and visualization—into a cohesive pipeline. This pipeline was then deployed onto a GitHub repository to make it accessible to researchers beyond the project team.

Scientific results (up to 800 words)

1. High-Resolution Micro-CT Imaging of GDL Structures

One of the key scientific achievements is the successful collection of 25 high-resolution 3D micro-CT scans of GDLs and the measurement of their corresponding porosity via pycnometer, which provided detailed images of their complex internal structures. The images captured features like pore spaces, fibers, and hydrophobic binder distribution, which are critical to understanding performance variations within the GDL. By using micro-CT tomography, the project achieved a non-destructive visualization of the internal GDL architecture, which traditionally would have required invasive methods.

These high-resolution volumes revealed details about the pore distributions, which are crucial for optimizing gas transport and liquid water management within PEMFCs.

2. AI-Based Segmentation of GDL and MPL Features

A major breakthrough in this project was the successful development of AI-based methods to automate the segmentation of key features within the 3D GDL and MPL volumes. By training convolutional neural networks (CNNs) on porosity thresholded micro-CT images, we were able to train models that automatically identified and segmented pores and fibers within the GDL. The models outperform the standard visual and Otsu threshold methodologies by learning to segment the fibers based on porosity thresholded scans. This does not only improve the precision of the segmentations but also skips the necessity to measure the porosity of the samples in an extra step.

The performance of the four 3D deep learning architectures (3D UNET, 3D VNET, 3D HRNET, and 3D SwinUNET) was benchmarked against each other, and the results demonstrated a significant improvement in both accuracy and speed while employing the 3D HRNET architecture in GDL and MPL segmentation. This was particularly important in the analysis of water transport within the GDL, where inaccuracies in segmentation can lead to flawed predictions of performance metrics such as tortuosity and permeability.

Quantitatively, the AI models achieved high accuracy in segmentation tasks, with an overall precision of over 90% in identifying the different phases (pore, material, and MPL) within the micro-CT images. This advancement not only provided a more reliable means of analyzing GDL structures but also opened the door for large-scale, high-throughput studies of GDLs in future research.

3. Quantitative Analysis of Key GDL Properties

Following the automated segmentation, a series of computer vision-based algorithms were developed to extract quantitative properties from the 3D GDL volumes. These properties are directly linked to the performance of the GDL in PEMFCs, making them critical for optimizing cell design. The primary properties extracted included:

1. **Porosity:** The AI-driven analysis provided a more accurate estimate of the GDL's pore space, which is essential for gas diffusion and water transport. The extracted porosity values were consistent with those reported in the literature but were obtained with a fraction of the time and effort.
2. **Pore Size Distribution:** One of the most important factors for understanding how the different distributions affects the reactant and product transport and the water management as well.
3. **Tortuosity Factor:** The tortuosity factor, which affects both gas and liquid transport in the GDL, was also calculated from the segmented images.
4. **Surface roughness calculation:** calculates the roughness of the first layer of the GDL
5. **Solid surface ratio:** This function outputs the material/pore ratio in the first layer, useful for modelling different properties structure based.

For the MPL-GDL segmentation algorithms, we also provided extra functions to extract the proper quantifications to better understand the

6. **Layer Thickness Calculation:** This function provides an accurate measurement of the thickness of the MPL across the GDL structure. By segmenting the MPL from the GDL, the algorithm calculates the layer thickness at various points, helping in the assessment of uniformity, which is crucial for ensuring consistent fuel cell performance.
7. **MPL Crack Analysis (Ratio, Size Distribution, etc.):** This feature automatically detects and analyzes cracks within the MPL. It provides critical metrics such as the crack-to-surface area ratio, crack size distribution, and the overall impact of these cracks on the structural integrity of the MPL, which can influence gas diffusion and cell durability.
8. **MPL Heatmap for Thickness Variation:** This visualization tool generates a heatmap to display the variations in MPL thickness across the GDL surface. Areas with significantly reduced

thickness can be easily identified, providing insights into manufacturing defects or areas prone to degradation during cell operation.

9. **MPL Intrusion Measurement:** This function quantifies the degree to which the MPL intrudes into the GDL structure. Accurate intrusion measurements are essential for optimizing the interface between these layers to enhance water management and gas transport.
10. **MPL and GDL Contact Surface Calculation:** This calculation determines the contact area between the MPL and GDL, which is critical for assessing how well the two layers integrate. A well-optimized contact surface ensures better electron and gas transfer, directly impacting the overall efficiency of the fuel cell.

4. Development of a User-Friendly Visualization Platform

To make these findings accessible to a broader audience, the project also developed visualization tools that allow researchers to interact with the 3D GDL volumes and explore the extracted data. Using advanced 3D rendering software, the team created interactive models where users could visualize pore networks, water pathways, and the distribution of hydrophobic materials. This feature proved invaluable for interpreting complex datasets and communicating the results to both researchers and industry professionals.

Furthermore, the development of this visualization platform allows for the generation of graphs and charts summarizing key metrics such as pore size distribution and tortuosity, making it easier to compare different GDL samples or experimental conditions. The ability to visualize these properties in a user-friendly interface enhances the tool's usability, providing a comprehensive way to interpret and present the data. All properties are then stored in a custom CSV file for further analysis by the experimentalist.

5. Software deployment

Once the pipeline was set, we deployed the software in GitHub by creating a user-friendly tutorial using Jupyter Notebook to allow the broader audience to run the code by themselves with minimal coding knowledge needed. This approach does not only facilitates the utilization of the tool but it also enables the future further development of the software in a version-based process thanks to GitHub and repository cloning.

Interpretation of the results (up to 400 words)

[Discuss the data obtained and describe the major scientific conclusions drawn.]

The results of this project demonstrate the successful integration of advanced imaging, machine learning, and computational analysis techniques to significantly improve the understanding of the gas diffusion layer (GDL) and microporous layer (MPL) structures within Proton Exchange Membrane Fuel Cells (PEMFCs). The AI-based segmentation methods, particularly with the 3D HRNET architecture, showcased a clear improvement in accuracy and efficiency when analyzing complex 3D micro-CT data. This automated approach not only bypassed the need for labor-intensive manual segmentation but also provided more precise identification of critical features such as pores, fibers, and cracks in the GDL and MPL. This level of precision ensures more accurate estimations of key performance parameters like porosity, tortuosity, and pore size distribution, which are fundamental to understanding gas and liquid transport in fuel cells. Moreover, the developed computer vision-based tools offer a deeper, more quantitative analysis of these properties. For instance, the calculation of surface roughness, solid surface ratio, and MPL intrusion provides insight into the structural variations that affect water management, gas diffusion, and overall fuel cell performance. The ability to detect and quantify cracks in the MPL

adds another dimension to the understanding of cell durability and failure mechanisms. These insights were previously challenging to obtain at this level of detail, especially through traditional visual methods.

The user-friendly visualization platform enhances the accessibility and interpretability of the data, allowing researchers to easily explore and compare different GDL samples. The interactive 3D models and heatmaps for thickness variation, along with the graphical representation of extracted metrics, make it easier to identify patterns, defects, or inconsistencies in the data. This visualization tool is a critical asset in communicating results to a broader audience, fostering collaboration between experimentalists and computational scientists.

In conclusion, the results of this project have advanced the state of the art in PEMFC research by providing a more accurate, automated, and efficient approach to characterizing GDL and MPL structures. These improvements will enable more informed design choices for fuel cells, optimizing key factors like water management and gas transport. The deployment of the software on GitHub ensures that these tools can be widely adopted and further developed, driving future research and innovation in hydrogen energy technologies.

Main achievements during the IREP related work (up to 250 words)

[Describe the main achievements during your stay at the site(s)]

1. **High-Resolution 3D Imaging:** We successfully collected 25 high-resolution micro-CT scans of GDLs, which provided detailed, non-invasive insights into their internal pore structure, fiber distribution, and hydrophobic binder application. This was a foundational step in visualizing the complex architecture of GDLs at a microscale level.
2. **Development of AI-Based Segmentation:** One of the major breakthroughs was the creation of AI-driven segmentation techniques, leveraging convolutional neural networks (CNNs), particularly the 3D HRNET model, to accurately identify and segment features like pores, fibers, and MPL cracks. This automation greatly reduced the time and effort required for data analysis while improving precision over traditional methods.
3. **Quantitative Feature Extraction:** New algorithms were developed to extract crucial metrics such as porosity, pore size distribution, tortuosity, and MPL layer thickness. These metrics are essential for understanding water management and gas transport properties in fuel cells.
4. **User-Friendly Visualization and Software Deployment:** The development of an interactive visualization platform allowed researchers to explore and analyze 3D GDL volumes with ease. The entire pipeline was successfully deployed on GitHub, making the tools accessible to a wider research community and enabling future improvements through collaborative development.

Difficulties during the IREP related work (up to 250 words)

[List problems and issues you had, completing out your research project: Did you get access to all the necessary equipment, facilities, databases, etc.?

If not, please specify the problems that occurred and list equipment that was not working or accessible.]

There were no external difficulties in completing out the research project.

Intended publications

[Explain where and how you expect to publish the outcomes of your project work. Include also anything already published (What and where?)]

We are planning to publish the results obtained during this research stay as a scientific publication in a scientific journal with energy technologies in the scope. This publication will be written in a collaborative fashion between both institutes.

Data management

[Describe the further usage and storage of project data]

Upon publication of the results, we are planning to make the data, model, and software open access to everyone.

Conclusions / additional comments

[Provide any other comments you might have on your work]

Did you complete the EC user questionnaire available at <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/RIsurveyUSERS> ? (necessary)

Yes No

Feedback – HSE, Ethics and Satisfaction

Please rate on a scale from 1 (excellent) to 5 (poor). Feel free to provide additional comments

Practical information on how to apply for IREP and the overall application process

1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

[Comment] The webpage for the proposal submission did not work.

Information provided, once your project was accepted, on how to proceed

1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

[Comment]

Support received at the site(s) regarding technical/scientific matters and logistics

Have you got sufficient support from the RI staff during the project? If not, please, specify the problems. Yes No

[Please specify any problems]

RI extension / upgrades required

In your opinion, is the RI needed to be upgraded? If yes, please give an explanation.
 Yes No

<i>[Please specify] Depending on the country, the funding might not be sufficient.</i>	
Problems with local regulations	Have you had any problems with regulations of the visited RI owner (HSE, lab working hours, etc.)? If yes, please, specify <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
<i>[Please specify]</i>	
Health and safety issues	Did you encounter any health or safety issue during your research? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
<i>[Please provide details]</i>	
Environment & Ethics	Did your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to the environment, to animals or plants? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
<i>[Please provide details]</i>	
Environment & Ethics	Did your research deal with endangered fauna and/or flora and/or protected areas? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
<i>[Please provide details]</i>	
Environment & Ethics	Did your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to humans, including research staff? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
<i>[Please provide details]</i>	
Environment & Ethics – Dual use	Does your research have the potential for military applications? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
<i>[Please provide details]</i>	
Environment & Ethics – Misuse	Does your research have the potential for malevolent /criminal/terrorist abuse? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
<i>[Please provide details]</i>	

Environmental issues	<p>Were any potentially dangerous substances (materials / gases etc.) released into the environment (atmosphere, water, or land)? Please provide details.</p> <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please provide details]</i>					
Ethics issues	<p>Are there any other ethics issues that should be taken into consideration? Please specify</p> <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please provide details]</i>					
Overall impression of communication and interaction after finishing your IREP related work	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>[Comment]</i>					
Suggestions for other international and EU facilities not included in StoRIES which you would use for your research					
<i>[Please provide suggestions for facilities, describe measurement / experiments you would like to perform]</i>					
Suggestions how StoRIES can improve future IREP programme, how to make the IREP more impactful on the energy storage technologies and how to enable the achievement of high TRL levels.					
<i>[Your suggestions]</i>					
Feedback – Pro-active Innovation Support					
Awareness	<p>Did you know about the pro-active innovation support of StoRIES.</p> <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please specify how you learned about the pro-active innovation support]</i>					
Personal experience	<p>Have you taken advantage of or benefited from the pro-active innovation support?</p> <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please provide details]</i>					

Information/service provided by the pro-active innovation support?	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

[Please provide details]

I declare that the above provided information and especially that information on the number of days visited the RI is correct.

I have read the [StoRIES privacy policy](#) for participation in the StoRIES Accesses and consent to participation and the associated data processing.

